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“MADONNA” – A UNIVERSAL TOOL FOR DEVELOPMENTAL LEARNING

One of the founders of constructivism, L. Vygotsky considers that learning must be preceded by the child's cognitive development. Therefore, teaching is the source of development. What is needed for teaching to be developmental? In order for the child to develop cognitively, it is necessary for him to learn. The question is: what should you learn, who should you learn, etc. The first question is answered in the document "general education national goals", which can be considered as a state order – we must teach everything that is necessary for the formation of a free personality, the bearer of national and general values. As for the second question, a child can learn from a teacher, a peer, a person older than him, and etc.

The concept of developmental learning is based on the student's immediate development zone. The "closest development zone" is the central concept of constructivism theory. This is the difference between the current level of the child's development and the potential level. The current level of development is the maximum of the child's abilities, that is, the upper limit of the difficulty of the tasks that the child can solve without the help of others, independently, while the potential level of development means the upper limit of the difficulty of the tasks that the child can solve with the help of someone else, a more competent peer, or the teacher. Basically, the teaching that takes place in the closest zone of development is the source of the child's development, and such tasks, which the child can perform independently, contribute less to his development. Based on the above, the modern teacher is faced with a number of challenges: he must correctly define the closest zone of the child's development and select the appropriate tasks for this zone, take into account that the task must be interesting and motivating for the student, fully meet the subject standards, be connected to the child's life experience, The art of scaffolding must be well mastered in order to provide help to the student at the right time and dose, observe the student's task performance process, evaluate the developing feedback, if necessary use differentiated learning approaches, remediation, etc.

In this difficult and important case, the teacher's help can be provided with the **developmental learning tool "Madona" (see table).**

Table 1

m	Macro concept and related main data: macro – difficult It is the first component of the word and means big, big, while the concepts are defined according to the national curriculum, As the basis of systematic and comprehensive knowledge of the subject. In this column, the essential data from the tasks will be entered.
a	association – (Lat.) It means to connect. In psychology, this is the kind of connection between representations, when one representation leads to another according to similarity, contrast or proximity. e.g. In our case, it will be the activation of previous knowledge related to the new task from the stock of knowledge that already exists in the student's mind.
d	dynamics – (gre.) By definition, it means the variability of any event, the course of development. In relation to the instrument under consideration, this will be the understanding and argumentation of the sequence of procedures to be performed by the student.
o	operate – (Lat.) any work, physical, mental. In this case, it means the correct performance of each procedure listed in the previous graph.
n	Innovation (lat. novatio) the student mentions, what was the news for him, he "triggered" when completing these tasks.
a	audience (lat. – auditorium) – the term has the meaning of a report, a lecture, etc. The unity of the listeners. In the reviewed instrument, this graph involves the presentation of the work in front of the class, its answers to the questions asked, the student's emotions when interacting with the audience, In general, the student reflects on the work done. However, the student himself decides how he will present his work to the audience.

By its very nature, "Madona" is a universal tool, because it can be used successfully by both the student and the teacher, and the student can also use it during the work process and during the presentation of work, while the teacher can use it when giving assignments and evaluating work.

Consider several examples of tasks using the "Madona" tool.

As for the tool intended for the teacher, due to its multi-functionality, we can use several variations of it: I represent the evaluation rubric and it is similar to the one intended for the student, with the difference that, depending on the teacher's wishes, it has four or five columns. The first column lists the evaluation criteria, and the rest - performance indicators according to the levels of maturity. II - It is used to observe the work of students. There are three-level graphs along each line, in which the teacher indicates which level corresponds to a particular student's work process or created product. The last column is intended for notes, where the teacher makes notes, based on which evidence he marked this or that level. These records will be used during the student's developmental assessment. III or short form is used for individual assessments. According to the levels, appropriate feedback is required.

As mentioned above, the presented tool is designed to help both students and teachers. But this alone does not exhaust its universality. It can be used by any subject teacher. The tool is flexible and allows you to use it when performing different types of tasks.

Pict. 1

(macro definition: Geometric transformations (symmetry) – VI cla.

according to the mathematics subject standard, the result to be achieved: The student should be able to demonstrate geometric transformations.

task conditions: Once upon a time, the neighboring princes (geo. Fifqia) of the kingdom invited me to the council. Princes (geo. Fifqia) decided to wear a new dress to the party and went to the best tailor in the kingdom, but unfortunately, the tailor could not become a tailor. Princes (geo. Fifqia) was forced to buy a dress for a student. I really wanted to learn, So that the dress came out beautiful, he decorated it with a collar, cuffs, pockets, buttons, relief lines, but despite this, the dress still didn't come out beautiful. princes (geo. Fifqia) was very worried, she didn't know what to do with the dress. Observe the drawings (pict.1). In your opinion, what are the flaws of the dress? How to correct these errors; In your opinion, how do you change your version of the dress? Model of the class dress.

m	Geometric transformations (symmetry) and related essential data, eg. Artistic details such as the collar, pocket, cuffs, relief lines on the gusset on the right and left sides of the dress are not symmetrically arranged.
a	The condition of symmetry; It is not necessary, previous knowledge is only connected to mathematics. It is completely possible, the student will remember, How to make a doll's dress in art class, how to fold the fabric twice before cutting out, so that both sides are the same on the folding line. Or at least for the New Year's Eve, cut out the whistles from the folded paper.
d	1. The collar It is narrow, the other side wide. You can't zoom in on the rounded part, It is necessary to narrow and round the wider part. 2. At the throat There are different number of lines Because making a new wreath is easier than removing the existing one, a third relief wreath must be added on the left side. 3. The left relief line coming out of the year must be extended and extended to the right. 4. The pockets are located at different heights. It is necessary to lift the right pocket up to the same height, because it is very close to the waistline and the pocket is not recognized. 5. The cuffs have different shapes and sizes. It is not possible to change any of them so that they are identical to each other.
o	The student first draws the axis of symmetry, then corrects all the flaws on the same drawing according to the rules of the symmetrical figure of the given figure and prepares the model of the dress to be presented to the class.
n	The news for the student was that he saw with his own eyes how useful and useful geometric transformations are, in particular the knowledge of symmetry to solve a specific existing problem.
a	The student describes the process of submitting his work, what questions were asked by the teacher and classmates, how he handled these questions, what he was satisfied with, what he struggled with, what he changed, if he had to do such a task again, etc.

evaluation rubric

appendix 1

Option 1

criteria	1 level	2 level	3 level
macro concept – Main data			
association			
dynamics			
operate			
novatio			
audience			

Option 2

N 1	name, surname	m	a	d	o	n	a	note
1								
2								
3								
4								
5								

Student:-----

Option 3

m	a	d	o	n	a	